

DIFFERENT TYPES OF ANNOUNCING THE INVISIBLE THINGS DURING THE OLD TESTAMENT

HOJJATOLLAH JAVANI

ABSTRACT

Announcing the invisible things has been important during the Jewish history,, thus numerous methods and tools have been used to find out the invisible things and there are generally three types of forecasting in the Old Testament; in the first type ,the seer forecasts through special tools like lot, water, arrows, and dreams, etc without any claim; in the second type, the magicianfore casts with the claim to change the affairs into the good or evil through using the special tools such as idol, animals organs and movements ,talking with dead ones, etc. this kind of necromancy was strongly criticized in the old Testament; in the third type, the prophet prophesies through the divine revelation and this was the called the prophecy during the old Testament prophesy. The prophet received the occultacles through the revelation and gave them to the people. The se oracles are classified into three sections including the stories of nations and past prophet's current and future events. The future events are classified into mundane and here after. The mundane seventh refer to the social events until the end of the world and the here after events refer to the resurrection, heaven and hell.